

The role of antioxidant defense systems in maize leaves under salt stress

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Salt stress affects general metabolic processes and enzymatic activities, leading to increased production of reactive oxygen species. During exposure to stress, antioxidant defense systems, in turn, begin to protect the cell from oxidative damage. The effect of various salt concentrations (0, 1, 2, 3% NaCl) on the hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and superoxide anion (O₂⁻) radicals, the activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD), ascorbate peroxidase (APX) and catalase (CAT) has been studied in the leaves of maize (*Zea mays* L.) plants. High levels of NaCl have been found to lead to an increase in H₂O₂ and (O₂⁻) content in the leaves. Significant changes in enzymatic activities and isoenzyme contents of SOD and APX were found. Thus, it was observed that the activity of SOD and APO increased at low concentrations (1 and 2% NaCl) of salt and decreased at high (3% NaCl) concentrations. The highest activity of CAT enzymes was detected at 2% and 3% NaCl.

Keywords: *Zea mays* L., salt stress, superoxide anion, hydrogen peroxide, superoxide dismutase, ascorbate peroxidase, catalase

INTRODUCTION

Salinity is one of the major abiotic stresses in arid and semiarid regions (Rengasamy et al., 2003). Salt stress induces a multitude of responses in plants, including morphological, physiological, biochemical, and molecular changes (Abd Elgawad et al., 2016). High salinity is one of the most important abiotic stress factors limiting plant growth and productivity of a wide variety of crops. Thus, increased soil salinity has become an increasingly important topic (Azooz et al., 2009). There is evidence that high salt concentrations cause an imbalance in cellular ions, resulting in ion toxicity and osmotic stress, leading to the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) that cause damage to DNA, lipids, and proteins (Kaya et al., 2015). Reactive oxygen species production is a usual biochemical event that occurs in plants. The reactive oxygen species such as superoxide (O₂⁻), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), hydroxyl radical (·OH), and singlet oxygen (¹O₂) are produced when electrons from the electron transport chains in mitochondria and chloroplasts are leaked and react with O₂ in the absence of other electron acceptors (Mittler, 2002). ROS are generated during normal cellular metabolism, but there is evidence that ROS production is increased when plants are subjected to biotic or abiotic stresses (Møler, 2007).

To mitigate the oxidative damage initiated by ROS, plants have developed a complex defense

antioxidative system, including low-molecular-mass antioxidants as well as antioxidative enzymes, such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT) and ascorbate peroxidase (APX) (Azevedo Neto et al., 2006). SOD catalyzes the dismutation of superoxide to hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and oxygen. Hydrogen peroxide, which is also toxic to cells, is detoxified by CAT peroxidases to water and oxygen. APX reduces H₂O₂ using ascorbate as an electron donor in the ascorbate-glutathione cycle (Sevengor et al., 2011).

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is one of the most significant C₄ cereal crops in the world, but it is known to be highly sensitive to saline stress (Kaya et al., 2018). Maize is the third most important cereal crop after rice and wheat and is grown under a broad spectrum of soil and climatic conditions. Although the response of the antioxidant defense systems of maize to abiotic stress has been studied by several researchers, under drought and salt stress conditions, currently there is not enough information about the comparative analysis of the antioxidant defense system during these stresses.

This study aimed to complete the collected data on the regulation of catalase (CAT), ascorbate peroxidase (APX), superoxide dismutase (SOD) enzyme activities, and isozyme composition during salt stress. In this study, the total activity and isoenzyme composition of CAT, APX, and SOD were evaluated in response to NaCl stress. The results of the presented studies showed that salt

stress induces complex and coordinated antioxidant defense responses in maize.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material and growth conditions:

Seedlings of the maize plant (*Zea mays* L.), which is a cereal crop, were cultivated in soil under controlled phytotron conditions (photoperiod – 14h/10h, t – 26 °C, light intensity - 600 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) based on the method presented by Hasan et al. (2006).

Histochemical detection of H_2O_2 : H_2O_2 was visually detected in the leaves of plants by using 3,3-diaminobenzidine (DAB) as a substrate (Szechyńska-Hebda et al., 2012). H_2O_2 was visualized as a reddish-brown coloration of the leaf blades and photographed.

Histochemical detection of superoxide anion radicals: Superoxide anion is detected with nitroblue tetrazolium (NBT). Superoxide ions react with NBT and appear as blue stains. The stained leaves can be photographed (Mahalingam et al., 2006).

Determination of the malondialdehyde (MDA) content. The main product of the lipid peroxidation in plant tissues-MDA was determined based on the reaction with thiobarbituric acid (TBT). The optical density of the supernatant was determined by the spectrophotometer ($\lambda=532$ and 600 nm) after the repeat centrifugation for 10 min, at 15,000g. The MDA content was calculated using an extinction coefficient of 155 ($\mu\text{m/g}$ fresh weight) with the subtraction of non-specific absorption at 600 nm. (Heath & Packer, 1968).

Determination of the protein content: The Bradford (1976) procedure was used for the appraisal of total soluble protein contents. Fresh leaf (500 mg) was finely homogenized in phosphate buffer and centrifuged at $2000 \times g$ for 10 min. To 1 ml of supernatant, 5 ml Coomassie Brilliant blue reagent was added, vortexed for 20 s, and measured the absorbance of the solution at 595 nm on a spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific Evolution 201, Japan).

Superoxide dismutase (SOD, EC 1.15.1.1) activity was determined at 450 nm using SOD Assay Kit (Sigma, Aldrich).

Catalase (CAT, EC 1.11.1.6) activity was determined by the change in optical density of the reaction mixture for 1 min at 240 nm (Nakano and Asada, 1981). The method is based on determining the rate of decomposition of hydrogen peroxide by catalase to form water and oxygen. The reaction mixture contained 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0), 2 mM of H_2O_2 , and 1 mM EDTA (pH 8.0).

The reaction was initiated by the addition of 50 mg of total protein. The activity was calculated in $\text{mmol}/(\text{mg protein min})$ based on a molar extinction coefficient: $e = 39.4 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Ascorbate peroxidase (APX, EC 1.11.1.11) activity was determined by the method of Nakano and Asada (1981) with some modifications. The method is based on the determination of the rate of decomposition of hydrogen peroxide by ascorbate to form water and dehydroascorbate. Optical density was recorded in a spectrophotometer at 290 nm. The assay mixture contained 90 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0), 0.1 mM EDTA, 0.65 mM ascorbate, and 1 mM of H_2O_2 . The reaction was initiated by the addition of 50 mg of total protein. The activity was calculated in $\mu\text{mol}/(\text{mg protein min})$ based on a molar extinction coefficient: $e = 2.8 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Statistical analysis: All experiments were performed in 3 replicates, and errors were calculated using the student's t-test statistical analysis program. When the value of $P < 0.01, 0.05$, the differences between the mean values were considered significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Histochemical analysis revealed the accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in damaged parts of maize plant leaves affected by salt stress. The collection of superoxide anion radicals in the leaves increased significantly with increasing salt concentrations (Fig. 1). As can be seen, the accumulation of superoxide radicals in leaves exposed to 2% and 3% NaCl is greater than that of 1% salt.

Fig. 1. Accumulation of superoxide anion radicals in leaves of maize exposed to salt stress.

H_2O_2 , the main indicator of stress, was not detected in the leaves of control plants, but the accumulation of H_2O_2 was observed under the NaCl effect. Figure 2 shows that the amount of H_2O_2 increases significantly with increasing

concentrations of NaCl (Fig. 2).

Malondialdehyde is a product of the peroxidation of unsaturated fatty acids in phospholipids, and the level of lipid peroxidation is an indicator of the damaging effects of free radicals on cell membranes under salt stress. The studies revealed that the amount of MDA increased with the increase in the concentration of NaCl in maize leaves. As can be seen in Fig. 3, the amount of MDA in leaf cells increased by approximately 2-fold in 2% salt medium and 2.8-fold in 3% salt medium compared to the control. Several studies have shown that salt stress produces alterations in the structure and composition of plasma membrane lipids, such as the increase in the degree of saturation of free fatty acids and an increase in free sterols, which leads to a decrease in the fluidity of cell membrane (Mansour et al., 2005). One of the studies reported that MDA plays a vital role in the salt tolerance of maize cultivars (Azevedo Neto et al., 2006).

Fig. 2. Accumulation of H_2O_2 in leaves of maize exposed to salt stress.

In the present study, all treatment samples (1%, 2%, and 3% NaCl) showed a significant decrease in the protein content of plants compared to their control. A similar result was reported by Parvaneh et al., (2011) working on *Portulaca oleracea* L. leaves who observed that leaf protein concentrations decreased with increasing salinity stress.

It was found that under the influence of 1% NaCl, the SOD activity in the leaf was stimulated compared to the control but the subsequent increase in salt inhibited the activity of the enzyme (Fig. 4A). Total SOD activity showed an inverse correlation to salt concentration, that is increasing salt concentrations caused diminished activity (Menezes-Benavente et al., 2004). During the electrophoretic analysis of the isoenzyme composition of the SOD enzyme, four isoforms in the leaves were observed on the electropherogram (Fig. 4B).

Fig. 3. Effect of salt stress on the content of MDA in maize leaves.

Table 1. Effect of salt stress on the protein content in maize

Example	Protein (mg g FW ⁻¹)
0% NaCl	0,171±0,01
1% NaCl	0,151 [*] ±0,0075
2% NaCl	0,143 [*] ±0,0071
3% NaCl	0,135 [*] ±0,0067

The studies revealed quite high (16.58 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mg}$ protein min) constitutive activity of APX in control plants (Fig. 5A). In the enzyme extract isolated from the leaves, the activity of APX increased depending on the concentration of salt, while inhibition was observed in the leaves of plants cultivated in a 3% NaCl medium (13.19 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mg}$ protein min). Similar results were found in the works of several scientists (Azevedo Neto et al., 2006.). According to the analysis of the isoenzyme composition of the ascorbate peroxidase enzyme, there are 5 isoforms of APX (APX1, APX2, APX3, APX4, and APX5) in leaf cells, which differ in their mobility (Fig. 5B).

The activity and isozyme composition of the catalase enzyme in leaves of maize plants were also studied under salt stress conditions (Fig. 6) In the leaves of plants grown in 1% NaCl medium, the activity of CAT increased 1.7-fold compared to the control, in 2% NaCl medium- 2.2-fold, and 3% NaCl medium - 2.5-fold. Two isoforms of catalase were detected in the enzyme extract isolated from the leaves of the maize plant (Fig. 6B). Depending on the salt concentration, an increase in the intensity of these isoforms was observed, which indicates an increase in the number of proteins corresponding to these isoforms (Carvalho et al., 2011). Although it performs the same function as catalase, the presence of isoforms in different parts of the cell makes APX more effective than catalase in neutralizing H_2O_2 during stress (Das and Roychoudhury, 2014; Rohman et al., 2019).

Fig.4. Activity (A) and isoenzyme composition (B) of the SOD enzyme in leaves of the maize plant exposed to salt stress: 1-0% NaCl, 2-1% NaCl, 3-2% NaCl, 4-3% NaCl

Fig. 5 Activity (A) and isoenzyme composition (B) of the APX enzyme in leaves of the maize plant exposed to salt stress: 1-0% NaCl, 2- 1% NaCl, 3- 2% NaCl, 4- 3% NaCl

Fig. 6. Effect of different concentrations of NaCl on the activity (A) and isozyme composition; (B) of CAT in the leaves of the maize plant: 1-0% NaCl, 2-1% NaCl, 3-2% NaCl, 4-3% NaCl

Analyzing the obtained results, it can be concluded that there is a synergism or, in other words, an inverse relationship between the activity of APX and CAT in the leaves of the maize plant at high concentrations of salt. It is believed that as a

result of stress, H₂O₂ accumulated in high amounts in cells is disposed of by other enzymes of the antioxidant defense system, including CAT and its amount decreases. As a result, the low amount of hydrogen peroxide, which is the substrate of APX,

leads to a decrease in the activity of the enzyme in the environment.

CONCLUSIONS

The activity of three enzymes subjected to salt stress has been studied comparatively in maize leaves. During the influence of different concentrations of salt (0,1,2 and 3%NaCl), the activities of CAT, APX, and SOD often play a vital role in the protection of plants from stress. An inverse correlation was observed between the activity of APX and CAT in maize. A decrease in the activity of APX was observed in the 3% NaCl medium against the background of the increase in the activity of CAT in maize leaves. This fact can be explained by the reduction of H₂O₂, the substrate of APX as a result of its utilization by CAT. During the analysis of the isoenzyme composition of antioxidant enzymes in maize leaves subjected to salt stress 5 isoforms of APX and 4 isoforms of SOD, and 2 isoforms of CAT were detected on the electrophorogram. Based on the research results, it can be concluded that plants respond to salt stress by regulating the activity and isozyme composition of antioxidant enzymes.

REFERENCES

- Rengasamy P., Chittleborough D., Helyar K.** (2003) Root-zone constraints and plant-based solutions for dryland salinity. *Plant and Soil*, **257(2)**: 249-260.
- Abd Elgawad H., Zinta G., Hegab M.M., Pandey R., Asard H., Abuelsoud W.** (2016) High salinity induces different oxidative stress and antioxidant responses in maize seedlings organs. *Frontiers in plant science*, **7(11)**: 276.
- Azooz M.M., Ismail A.M., Elhamd M.A.** (2009) Growth, lipid peroxidation and antioxidant enzyme activities as a selection criterion for the salt tolerance of maize cultivars grown under salinity stress. *Int. J. Agric. Biol*, **11(1)**: 21-26.
- Kaya C., Ashraf M., Sonmez O.** (2015) Promotive effect of exogenously applied thiourea on key physiological parameters and oxidative defense mechanism in salt-stressed *Zea mays* L. plants. *Turk. J. Bot.*, **39(5)**: 786–795.
- Mittler R.** (2002) Oxidative stress, antioxidants and stress tolerance. *Trends Plant Sci.*, **7(9)**: 405–410.
- Møller I.M., Jensen P.E., Hansson A.** (2007) Oxidative modifications to cellular components in plants. *Annu. Rev. Plant Biol.*, **58**: 459-481.
- De Azevedo Neto A.D., Prisco J.T., Enéas-Filho J., Abreu C.E.B. de, Gomes-Filho E.** (2006) Effect of salt stress on antioxidative enzymes and lipid peroxidation in leaves and roots of salt-tolerant and salt-sensitive maize genotypes. *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, **56(1)**: 87-94.
- Parvaneh R., Tavakoli S., Hosseini S.M.** (2011) Studying of salinity stress effect on germination, proline, sugar, protein, lipid and chlorophyll content in Purslane (*Portulaca oleracea* L.) leaves. *J. Stress Physiol. & Biochem.* **8(1)**: 182-193.
- Sevengor S., Yasar F., Kusvuran S., Ellialtioglu S.** (2011) The effect of salt stress on growth, chlorophyll content, lipid peroxidation and antioxidative enzymes of pumpkin seedling. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, **6(21)**: 4920-4924.
- Kaya C., Akram N.A., Ashraf M., Sonmez O.** (2018) Exogenous application of humic acid mitigates salinity stress in maize (*Zea mays* L.) plants by improving some key physico-biochemical attributes. *Cereal Research Communications*, **46(1)**: 67-78.
- Hasan R., Kawasaki M., Taniguchi M., Miyake H.** (2006) Salinity stress induces granal development in bundle sheath chloroplasts of maize, an NADP-malic enzyme-type C₄ plant. *Plant production science*, **9(3)**: 256-265.
- Szechyńska-Hebda M., Skrzypek E., Dąbrowska G., Wędzony M., van Lammeren A.** (2012) The effect of endogenous hydrogen peroxide induced by cold treatment in the improvement of tissue regeneration efficiency. *Acta Physiologiae Plantarum*, **34(2)**: 547-560.
- Mahalingam R., Jambunathan N., Gunjan S.K., Faustin E., Weng H.U.A., Ayoubi P.** (2006) Analysis of oxidative signaling induced by ozone in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Plant, Cell & Environment*, **29(7)**: 1357-1371.
- Heath R.L., Packer L.** (1968) *Photoperoxidation in isolated chloroplasts*. *Archives of Biochemistry and Biophysics*, **125(1)**: 189–198.
- Bradford M.** (1976) A rapid and sensitive method for the quantitation of microgram quantities of protein utilizing the principle of protein-dye binding. *Anal. Biochem*, **72**: 248-254.
- Nakano Y., Asada K.** (1981) Hydrogen peroxide is scavenged by ascorbate-specific peroxidase in spinach chloroplasts. *Plant and Cell Physiology*, **22(5)**: 867-880.
- Mansour M.M.F., Salama K.H.A., Ali F.Z.M., Abou Hadid A.F.** (2005) Cell and plant response to NaCl in *Zea mays* L. cultivars differing in salt tolerance. *Gen. Appl. Plant Physiol.*, **31(1-2)**: 29-41.
- Menezes-Benavente L., Kernodle S.P., Margis-Pinheiro M., Scandalios J.G.** (2004) Salt-

induced antioxidant metabolism defenses in maize (*Zea mays* L.) seedlings. *Redox report*, **9(1)**: 29-36.

Carvalho R.F., Piotto F.A., Schmidt D., Peters L.P., Monteiro C.C., Azevedo R.A. (2011) Seed priming with hormones does not alleviate induced oxidative stress in maize seedlings subjected to salt stress. *Scientia Agricola*, **68(5)**: 598–602.

Das, K., Roychoudhury, A. (2014) Reactive oxygen species (ROS) and response of

antioxidants as ROS-scavengers during environmental stress in plants // *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, **2**: 53.

Rohman M.M., Islam M.R., Naznin T., Omy S.H., Begum S., Alam S.S., Hasanuzzaman M. (2019) Maize production under salinity and drought conditions: Oxidative stress regulation by antioxidant defense and glyoxalase systems. *Plant Abiotic Stress Tolerance: Agronomic, Molecular and Biotechnological Approaches*, 1-34.

Duz stresinin təsiri zamanı qarğıdalı yarpaqlarında antioksidant müdafiə sisteminin rolu

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Azərbaycan Respublikası Elm və Təhsil Nazirliyi Molekulyar Biologiya və Biotexnologiyalar İnstitutunun Hüceyrənin membran sistemləri laboratoriyası, Bakı, Azərbaycan

Duz stresi metabolik proseslərə və fermentlərin fəaliyyətinə təsir edərək, hüceyrədə oksigenin fəal formalarının (OFF) əmələ gəlməsinə və toplanmasına səbəb olur. Stres şəraitində hüceyrədə fəaliyyət göstərən fermentativ və qeyri-fermentativ antioksidant müdafiə sistemləri hüceyrəni zədələnmədən qoruyur. Məqalədə NaCl duzunun təsirinə məruz qalmış qarğıdalı (*Zea mays* L.) bitkisinin yarpaqlarında əmələ gələn hidrogen peroksid (H_2O_2) və superoksid anion (O_2^-) radikallarının söndürülməsində iştirak edən superoksiddismutaza (SOD), askorbat peroksidaza (APO) və katalaza (KAT) fermentlərinin fəallığı tədqiq edilmişdir. NaCl-un yüksək qatılıqlarında H_2O_2 və superoksid anion radikalının miqdarının artması aşkar edilmişdir. Duzun nisbətən aşağı qatılıqlarında (1% və 2% NaCl) SOD və APO-nun fəallığının artdığı, yüksək qatılığında (3% NaCl) isə azaldığı müşahidə edilmişdir. Katalaza fermentinin ən yüksək fəallığı 2%-li duz stresində aşkar edilmişdir.

Açar sözlər: *Zea mays* L., duz stresi, superoksid anionu, hidrogen peroksid, superoksid dismutaza, askorbat peroksidaza, katalaza